

Availability and Utilization of AI and I.C.T Resources in Content Delivery among Kano Municipal Local Government Teachers, Kano Nigeria

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This study assessed the Availability and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Information and communication technology resources in the teaching of chemistry in secondary schools within Kano Municipal, Kano State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was employed, involving the entire population of 46 chemistry teachers across 31 schools. Data were collected using AI/ICT availability checklist and a 20- items AI/ICT Resources Questionnaire(AI/ICT-RQ) validated by experts with reliability coefficient of 1.00 For AI/ICT availability checklist and 0.93 for AI/ICT-RQ. Descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the questions. The null hypothesis were tested using Biserial Correlation with NCSS 2020. The findings revealed that, apart from desktop computers, laptops, and some molecular visualization tools, most AI/ ICT facilities such as projectors, interactive boards, virtual assistants and chatbots were not available, lack of utilization of ICT tools was absent in content delivery among teachers as they mainly uses internet and Microsoft excel for updating lesson notes and result computation by themselves respectively. From the analysis, no significant relationship was found between availability and utilization of ICT/AI resources. Based on the study findings, students can develop interest in using AI and several study skills that will enhance their academic performance across all gender. Recommendations were made: education authorities improve the provision and accessibility of AI/ICT tools, offer training, motivation and proper orientation programs to provide an effective classroom integration.

Keywords:
Availability,
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Introduction

Science education is a field of study that exposes learners to content as well as the methodology of acquiring scientific knowledge. It acquaints students with basic knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed for future work in science and related fields (Celestine & Omorogbe, 2013). This type of education takes place in a formal school setting under the auspices of a science

educator who is professionally qualified to moderate scientific activity in the classroom with the use of appropriate pedagogies. Scientific knowledge is relevant and applicable to all areas of life endeavors, without which life on the planets is miserable and primitive. For instance, the production of essential human needs such as soap of all kinds, creams, drinks, petroleum and its by products, clothing, drugs, household utensils, and chemicals for preservation of food items

as well as textiles are all products of the principles of chemistry (Babajide, 2015).

Chemistry is a popular subject among senior secondary schools in Nigeria owing to its nature. It addresses the needs of the majority through its relevance, functionality, content, practice and application (Emendu, 2014). Chemistry can be said to be the study of the nature, composition and properties of matter and the changes it undergoes (Ojokuku 2016).

Chemistry is one of the core science subjects (these are, Biology, Chemistry, Physics and Agriculture), taught in all senior secondary schools in Nigeria and it is assumed to be abstract in nature. Chemistry is a central science that cuts across all sciences and its importance cannot be over emphasized. Chemistry is fundamental in the industrialization world. Today, the world is seen as a global village meanwhile, this perception of globalization is not unconnected with industrialization in which chemistry is central. This work anchored on the identification of methodologies that may adduce the modus operandi of teaching this central or core science called chemistry. However chemistry must be taught at the secondary school level by experts who are thoroughly grounded in chemistry education (Zudonu, 2011). This because they are specialist abreast and equip with Chemistry pedagogy which is how to go about teaching their learners (Zudonu, 2011). Adeyomo (2010) argued that the teaching methods has gone beyond traditional methods which makes the integration of artificial intelligence and information technology very important in science classes.

The link between AI and education comprises three areas: learning with AI (using AI tools in the classroom), learning about AI (its technologies and techniques)

and preparing for AI (enabling all citizens to understand the potential impact of AI on human life). Unesco (2019).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and information and communication technology (ICT) resources have emerged as popular topics in recent years, with different applications in the educational fields Abuhassan, Awae and Daud (2024). In chemistry education, there is growing interest in incorporating AI and ICT into various aspects of the curriculum. These include laboratory experiments, simulations, virtual laboratories, data analyses, and assessments. This demonstrates the importance of AI and ICT in the teaching and learning processes of Marquez, Barrios and Mendez (2023).

AI and ICT are two different technological resources comprising different applications in educational systems. Maslej & Fattorini 2023 further explained that AI is computer software that can perform tasks that typically require human intelligence and perform difficult tasks such as seeing, understanding, and responding to spoken or written language, analyzing data, and making recommendations. AI and ICT are connected but differ in different contexts. Artificial intelligence is about making machines act like humans. Therefore, the integration of AI in chemistry instruction involves a range of approaches, such as intelligent tutoring systems, virtual labs, and personalized learning platforms, as suggested by Gazztaiger (2020).

In contrast to traditional lecture-based teaching, AI technologies provide interactive and engaging learning experiences that can help students build their knowledge more effectively (Tyagi and Chahal (2022). Kim (2024) examined how the utilization of AI in chemistry education revolutionizes the way students learn, process, and apply chemistry

knowledge in various context. Through the use of these technologies, students can access an easy and personalized learning environment through positive reasoning and perception that adapts to their learning style and pace and provides real-time feedback and assistance (Chiu 2021). They also facilitate simulations and virtual laboratory experiments, allowing students to observe molecular interactions and chemical reactions in ways that are not possible in traditional laboratory settings (Shi 2021). Therefore, the integration of AI into chemistry education creates a more engaging, interactive, and efficient learning experience for students and contributes to the improvement of academic performance by optimizing instructional processes and reducing students' learning difficulties.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been defined by various scholars from different perspective. Mueen, Asadullah, et al. (2013) defined ICT to include an electronic network-embodiment complex hardware and software linked by a vast array of technical protocols. Ufuophu and Ayobami (2012) observed that ICTs include the Internet, satellites, cables, data transmission, and computer-assisted equipment. However, ICT facilities, tools and resources can be used to process, store, preserve, access, retrieve and disseminate information with ease (Ziraba, 2012).

According to Kirwan, Awati, and Pratt (2025), ICT refers to the infrastructure and components that enable modern computing to improve the way humans create, process and share data or information with each other.

On the other hand, Onwubiko (2011) sees ICT as any technology that is used in producing and for distributing information. It is a broad concept that encompasses the gathering (acquisition), organization

(packaging), storage and retrieval for disseminating information that can be in textual or numeric (books and documents), pictorial and vocal forms (audio-visual) using a combination of all the above (multimedia) including computers and telecommunication facilities.

According to the United Nations (2012), there are various types of technologies are currently used in school mostly in Europe and America. These technologies are uncommon in the management of schools in Africa. These include computers in the classroom, class websites, class blogs wireless, classroom microphones, mobile devices, interactive whiteboards, digital video-on-demand, online media and online study tools.

The Chinese proverb remains appropriate for today's classroom and students as mentioned by Confucian Philosopher Xunzi (312-230 BC) "Tell me, I'll forget. Show me, I'll remember and involve me, I will understand." As chemistry is perceived to be abstract in nature where students can not grasp difficult concepts, Limited teaching resources, outdated teaching methods, heavy teacher workload, interactive demonstrations using AI tools, visual labs, automated assessment and digital record keeping could be useful to solve such problems.

Information and Communication Technology plays a major role in the education sector, by improving the quality, effectiveness, and efficiency of learning, research and educational management worldwide (Olusesan & Emmanuel, 2016). Kameswari (2011) also, pointed out that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a communication tool used in educational knowledge transfer process especially in tertiary institutions. ICT has the potential to support and improve education across the curriculum between

teachers and students. Therefore, the use of ICT cannot be ignored by teachers or students in ways not previously possible, creating new learning and teaching possibilities, enhancing achievements and extending interactions with local and global communities (Ekerete & Ekanem, 2015), and it is believed that it will help teachers acquire better skills in imparting knowledge effectively (Oye, Shallsaku & Lahad, 2012). The Internet is expanding access to resources such as e-books, journals, expanded abstracts and periodicals for both students and teachers such that no institution can rely only on traditional printed materials to perform effectively (Etebu, 2010).

The Global ICT Report (2012) showed that Nigeria ranked 112 out of 142 countries surveyed for network readiness to participate and benefit from ICT development. Many ICT resources are not available for effective teaching and learning and few are accessed and utilized by teachers (Nwana, Ofoegbu and Egbe, 2017). However, ICT's utilization is determined by its integration and accessibility in the curriculum. Meanwhile, the integration of ICT into education is still a critical issue that require urgent attention (Bhukuvhani, Zezekwa & Sunzuma, 2011).

Many studies have shown that ICT tools are unavailable. Apagu and Wakili (2015) revealed that computers, television sets, CCTV etc are not adequately available. Idoko and Ademu (2010) find out that ICT availability is often one of the most important obstacles to technology adoption and integration in learning. Umeh and Okonkwo (2014) reported a high level of availability of ICT resources but a decried lack of accessibility for successful utilization in content delivery. It is arguable

that an available resource that cannot be accessed by users is as good as not being available.

Therefore, this research aimed to assess the availability and utilization of AI and ICT in content delivery among chemistry teachers in Kano State.

Statement of the Problem

Today, the education system worldwide has certainly been affected positively by the influence of Artificial Intelligence and Information and Communication Technology (ICT). According to Abdul Salaam (2011), ICT has the potential to accelerate, enrich and deepen their skills motivate and engage students in learning help relate school experiences to work practices help create economic viability for tomorrow workers contribute to radical changes in schools strengthen teaching and provide opportunities for connection between school and the world.

As enormous as the benefits and roles of AI and ICT are at every level of the educational system, many challenges abound and prevent effective and efficient teaching and learning with ICT and AI tools. The most significant of these appear to be the unavailability and poor utilization of resources for teaching. Irrespective of jet age, some teachers find it difficult to operate devices such as computers, which is an indication that they cannot utilize ICT tools even when available.

The unavailability of these tools is related a lack of funds. UNESCO recommend that 26% of the national budget or 5% of the gross domestic product (GDP) should be spent on education. The truth of the matter is that non-utilization of and poor access to Artificial Intelligence and Communication Technology

in Nigerian schools and some developing countries in Africa seem to affect ICT utilization at all levels of education, thereby jeopardizing achievement and competitiveness globally (Adenuga, Owoyele & Adenuga, 2011).

Despite the statement made by the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) in 2013 on its National Policy of Education to provide adequate infrastructure and develop capacity for the effective utilization of Information and Communication Technology, many studies have shown the unavailability of ICT infrastructures. Ngwu (2014) and Tella (2011) mentioned that ICT resources are not adequately available, Idoko and Ademu (2010) found out that ICT availability is one of the major obstacles to ICT utilization. Mbuk (2010) mentioned that ICT education in Nigeria is yet to be enforced or explored and ICT tools for teaching and learning are yet to receive the attention it deserves (Obahiagbon and Osahon, 2014). Therefore, this study will appraise the availability of ICT tools if available, do teachers utilize them during chemistry content delivery?

Objectives of the Study

1. Identify the available ICT/AI tools for teaching Chemistry in Secondary School of Kano Municipal.
2. Assess the extent of ICT and AI utilization in content delivery among chemistry teachers.

Research Questions

1. What are the available AI and ICT tools for teaching chemistry?
2. To what extent are AI and ICT tools used for chemical content delivery among teachers?

Research Hypothesis

- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the availability and utilization of AI and ICT tools among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.
- H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the availability and utilization of ICT tools in content delivery among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.

Methodology

This study was a descriptive survey. The population of the study consisted of all 46 chemistry teachers in senior secondary schools of Kano Municipal local government under the Kano State Senior Secondary Management Board (KSSSMB), which was used as a sample due to its small population size. Two (2) instruments were used for data collection the; AI/ICT availability checklist with a reliability coefficient of 1.00, which consisted of ten (10) items. The second instrument was the Information and Communication Technology Resource Questionnaire (AI/ICT-RQ), with a reliability coefficient of 0.93. The instrument was validated by experts from the Department of Education and Science and Technology of Education (STE). It consists of 20 multiple choice items based on a 4-point Likert scale. Biserial correlation was employed to test this hypothesis because the independent variable (availability of AI/ICT tools) was dichotomous and the dependent variable (utilization of ICT/AI tools) was measured on a continuous scale.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the available AI and ICT tools for teaching chemistry?

Table 1: Availability of AI/ICT Resources for Teaching Chemistry

S/N	AI & ICT Tools	Available		Not Available		Decision
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	
1.	Virtual assistant	10	21.7	36	78.3	NA
2.	Tape Recorders	16	34.8	30	65.2	NA
3.	Image recognition	20	43.5	26	56.5	NA
4.	Chatbots	20	43.5	26	56.5	NA
5.	Interactive Board	7	15.2	39	84.8	NA
6.	Desktop Computers	33	71.7	13	28.3	A
7.	Laptop	28	60.9	18	39.1	A
8.	Molecular visualization tools	31	67.4	15	32.6	A
9.	Projector	14	30.4	32	69.6	NA
10.	Software for Chemistry	13	28.3	33	71.7	NA

Key: NA (not available), A (available).

Table 1 presents the results on the availability of ICT resources in Kano Municipal Senior Secondary Schools. It showed that, except for Computers and Laptops all other AI and ICT resources are not available. The sampled schools lacked chatbots, interactive boards, virtual assistants, etc.

Research Question 2: To what extent are AI and ICT tools utilized by teachers for chemistry content delivery?

To answer this research question, the mean and standard deviation were used as shown in the table below, to determine the utilization of available ICT resources among the teachers.

Table 2: Utilization of ICT/AI tools among teachers

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1.	Use of laptop for Chemistry lesson preparation	46	2.26	1.08	NU
2.	Use of the internet and AI in preparing Chemistry Practical	46	2.39	1.02	NU
3.	Use of Multimedia projectors for Chemistry teaching	46	1.93	1.14	NU
4.	Browsing via AI in updating Chemistry lesson notes	46	3.28	0.91	U
5.	Video/audio in AI for drilling of students to learn	46	2.32	1.09	NU
6.	Use of Microsoft Word Excel for result computation	46	2.58	1.12	U
7.	Use of virtual assistants in Chemistry Laboratory sessions	46	2.10	1.10	NU
8.	Use of e-mail to communicate with Chemistry students	46	1.76	1.03	NU
9.	Use of Microsoft Word Power Point for presentation	46	2.02	1.12	NU
10.	Use of Interactive Board for Chemistry content delivery	46	2.15	1.11	NU
Overall:			2.28	1.07	Not Utilized

Key: NU (Not Utilized); U (Utilized)

Table 2 shows that the ICT resources mentioned were not used in the content delivery of chemistry instructions. However,

teachers responded that they use the internet and artificial intelligence to update chemistry lesson notes and excel to compute students'

results. The respondents maintained that the use of the internet and AI related tools was not provided by the school, it is mostly for personal use.

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the availability and

utilization of ICT tools among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.

The data obtained from section A of the AI/ICT-RQ and that of the AI/ICT checklist were subjected to biserial correlation to determine if there was any relationship between availability and utilization of AI and ICT tools.

Table 3: Biserial correlations between availability and utilization of AI and ICT tools among teachers

Correlation r	lower 95.0% C.L of p	Upper 95.0% C.L of p	r ²	Count N	NO/N P	test for p=0	probability level
0.1967	-0.1613	0.5174	0.0387	46	0.5652	1.079	0.2808

The Biserial Correlation between the availability and utilization of AI and ICT tools among chemistry teachers, shown in Table 3.7 was found to have a low positive relationship, which is not statistically significant ($r_{bi}=0.196$; $p=0.281$, $c=46$). Therefore, the null hypothesis stated above is upheld. This implies that there is a positive relationship between availability and utilization, thus travelling along the same

trajectory, if availability goes up, then utilization might also goes up and vice versa, but since they are not statistically significant, it is concluded that availability is not the cause of utilization.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the availability and Utilization of AI and ICT tools in content delivery among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.

Table 4: Biserial Correlations between the Availability and Utilization of AI and ICT tools in content delivery.

Correlation r	Lower 95.0% C.L of p	Upper 95.0% C.Lof p	r ²	Count N	NO/N P	test for p=0	probability level
0.14	-0.2106	0.4768	0.0217	46	0.5652	0.803	0.4217

From the data generated through a biserial correlation between availability and utilization of ICT tools among teachers in Table 3.8, $r_{bi}=0.14$, $c=46$, and $p=0.422$, which is greater than .05, makes it statistically insignificant. The correlation here showed a very low positive correlation; thus, there was a relationship between the availability and utilization of ICT tools that was not statistically significant. In

other words, availability does not ensure the utilization of AI and ICT tools among chemistry teachers, eventhough utilization can only happen when the AI and ICT resources are available. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained.

The analysis clearly describe how lack of AI tools directly have impact on chemistry content delivery, the nature of the subject (chemistry) requires atomic, molecular and reaction

visualization, however, in the absence of AI powered visualization platforms and virtual laboratories, teachers would find it difficult to demonstrate such concepts simply and interactively with students, leaving them on total rote memorization, misconception in real time which results in poor engagement and performance.

Discussion

Data analysis for research question one (1) shows that ICT/AI tools such as computers, laptops and molecular visualization tools are available. The remaining tools, that is, image recognition, tape recorders, interactive boards, chatbots, and chemistry software are not available.

The study shows that there is a positive relationship between the availability and utilization of ICT tools, which is not significant among chemistry teachers. Eventhough desktops and laptops are fairly available, teachers have no access to them, as they are only used for administrative purposes.

These findings are in agreements with those of several other studies, such as Abdul-Salaam (2012), Bitok (2012), Achimugu (2016), Mavellas, Wellington and Samuel (2016), Osuafor (2016), Bunkure(2016) and Nkomo (2013),who agreed that ICT facilities are not readily available. Amuchie (2015) mentions that availability is very low. Njelita and Emendu (2015) stated that ICT and AI resources are not available, except computers.

The reason for the relationship between availability and utilization in this study is that we can utilize only what is available. Most of the schools in this study lacked ICT and AI facilities. Some of the available tools (computers and laptops) in the schools are not utilized, which explains why there is no

significant relationship between availability and utilization.

Hooda et al. (2022) proved that the use of AI and ICT helps streamline the process of grading and assessment in chemistry education. The use of AI-powered assessment tools helps teachers grade students work more quickly and accurately, reducing grading time and improving consistency Volkova 2020).

The results in Table 2 show low accessibility to ICT tools among teachers which resulted in low utilization. The ones they usually have access to, mostly, are not provided by the schools authority, but by themselves. The null hypothesis tested showed that there is a positive relationship between availability and utilization of ICT tools, but this is not statistically significant. This showed that accessibility before utilization can become effective, but accessibility does not assure utilization among teachers. Therefore, it can be concluded that hypothesis 2 is upheld. These findings are in line with those of Aramide et al. (2013), who found a low level of accessibility and a positive relationship between accessibility and usage. Augustine, Daud and Kamaruddin (2018) confirmed the low levels of ICT accessibility. Makinde et al. (2018) and Umeh and Okonkwo (2014) have demonstrated low accessibility.

The results in Table 3 indicate a low utilization of ICT tools among chemistry teachers. This implies that chemistry teachers do not use ICT tools for instruction delivery. These findings agree with those of Aramide, Olajo and Adekanye (2013), Ukpong (2016), and Makinde, Abdullahi and Bolaji (2018), who showed low levels of utilization. Njelita and Emendu (2015) assured teachers that they do not use ICT tools in teaching. Mavellas et al. (2016) and Wordu and Emamorose (2017) confirmed a lack utilization of ICT tools among

teachers. Ademiluyi (2019) showed that ICT tools were not used.

Furthermore, while previous studies mostly focused on ICT, this study expands the discussion to comprises both ICT and AI resources, and highlighting their closely absence condition in Kano municipal secondary schools classrooms. This contributes new evidence that chemistry teachers remain unable to incorporate emerging AI-driven learning platforms even when the basic ICT devices are available, thereby limiting innovative approaches towards content delivery.

Conclusions

Conclusively, ICT/AI resources for teaching chemistry except for desktop computers and laptops are not available. The level of ICT/AI and AI utilization of available tools is low among chemistry teachers in content delivery. This shows a relationship between availability and utilization which was not statistically significant. Also, there is lack of utilization of ICT/AI resources for chemistry content delivery among teachers, except in two areas; result computation and updating of lesson notes via the internet and a significant relationship was established between the availability and utilization of ICT tools among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.

Recommendations

1. AI/ICT resources should be made available to all schools, most importantly colleges of education and universities where teachers are trained, getting use of ICT/AI resources, while under training can help boost their confidence and competency, which, on the other hand, will make utilization even easier.
2. Responsible bodies such as the Ministry of Education, Education Boards, Policy Makers, and Schools Authority should

ensure that teachers have easy access to ICT tools.

3. The lack of Utilization of ICT resources in content delivery among teachers was mostly due to their mindset; in this study, they claimed to have the competency, but still lack of utilization was discovered. This shows that they need motivation, pressure and proper orientation to curtail their mindset, have confidence, and to know that ICT resources are not created specifically for computer subjects only.

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